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UNIVERSITÀ
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PRIN-MARMOT

D3.3

Data Management Plan

Version 1.4 - December 2025

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1 Revision history

Version	Date	Author	Main changes
v1.0	20240115	Odetti; Ferretti	Initial version
v1.1	20240604	Ferretti; Colombo; Carotenuto	Paragraphs updates; partners contributions to data description
v1.2	20241231	Ferretti; Colombo; Carotenuto; Karaki; Odetti; Aracri; Azzaro; Rolando.	First draft released
v1.3	20251211	Aracri	Folders structure
v1.4	20260302	Aracri	Folders structure added “corollary” folder
v1.5	20260319	Aracri	Folders structure added “Data Integration Files” folder

2 Introduction

MARMOT has a specialized **Data Management Plan (DMP)**, crucial, especially when embracing **FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. This deliverable focuses on ensuring data integrity and transparency while promoting collaboration and long-term usability of the dataset acquired during the project.

The DMP is a structured, living document that grows with the project. It is used to declare how the data is produced, how it will be stored and how it will be shared (if possible).

It must be conceived as **“Operating Instructions”** of our data, and it should be:

- concise**: avoid long descriptions, it is not a dissertation. Use clear sentences that give precise information
- schematic**: use tables and bullet points as much as possible
- precise**: avoid phrases like “we expect a huge size of data” or “data will be available”. They only serve to waste the time of those who write it and those who read it. Quantify: for example, we expect max 50 GB; data will be available in Zenodo upon publication of the paper
- specific**: do not copy from templates. Each research is unique, each institution has its own procedures, each project is a different story
- coherent**: write only what you are certain of, if you don't know something, say so.

3 Development

These sections will detail core requirements that should be addressed when developing a DMP, including data collection, storage, metadata standards, sharing, and long-term preservation-all aligned with the FAIR principles.

This approach sets a precedent for FAIR data management in marine robotics, advancing both technology and knowledge for ocean exploration.

Data Lifecycle

Data Management Plan

<https://images.app.goo.gl/FrFU9j7Txdy7j9A69>

4 Core Requirements for Data Management Plan

When developing robust data management plans, the following topics should be addressed and the following questions being answered:

Administrative data

ID: 2022KBASSY (Project Code)

Funder: European Union – Next Generation EU under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Mission 4 Education and Research - Component 2 From Research to Business – Investment 1.1

Grant Reference Number: CUP B53D23002740006

Project Name: Modular Alpine Robotic Monitoring Tools - MARMOT

Project Description:

- Nature of the Research Project: The MARMOT project focuses on developing advanced robotic technology specifically designed for monitoring high mountain lakes in the European Alps. The primary goal is to create a modular and portable robotic platform capable of conducting persistent environmental monitoring in these rapidly changing and sensitive ecosystems, which are affected by climate change and human activities. The research involves an interdisciplinary approach that integrates robotics, environmental science, and data management to enhance the understanding of alpine environments and their ecological status.

- Research Questions:

MARMOT will try to answer a series of questions reported here in a colloquial way. The product to be created will be a system of robots, sensors and techniques to better understand the characteristics of Alpine Lakes, answering the following main question:

"What does MARMOT need to become a tool used by scientists all over the world in remote areas?"

Robotics and IoT:

- Can an ASV become a comfortable Backpack? Can a researcher transport such a vehicle on a mountain trail with all the sensors that he requires for multiple analysis or will it be too heavy?
- Can an ASV operate autonomously for long periods in Alpine Lakes? Will Power consumption affect the operational time of a Backpack-ASV? Which is the best communication strategy to maximise duration?
- Can an ASV autonomously locate in the middle of a mountain lake with new techniques? Can such a Backpack-ASV or its subsystems become market products?
- Which is the best communication policy, storage and management for sampled data?
- Can an IoT infrastructure mounted on a Backpack-ASV interact with citizens to increment data transmission?
- What about security issues for hacking and vandalism?

Sensors:

- Can we integrate low-cost sensors in a Backpack-ASV technology in order to study physical and bio-optical trends along the water column and in the horizontal scale?
- Can low cost and lightweight sensors perform analysis with a good degree of accuracy?
- Can low-cost air-quality sensors identify potential airborne pollution events in remote areas?
- Can a Watersampler be integrated on Backpack-ASV in a useful way? Can researchers transport the collected water on a mountain trail or will it be too heavy?

Monitoring:

- Can a comprehensive assessment of release of major ions and trace elements in glacial meltwaters be performed through repeated measurements and sampling?
- Can the monitoring of air quality and aerobiology be important for understanding Alpine Lakes chemistry and microbiology ?
- Can potential anthropogenic impacts be assessed with a robot in order to better understand pollutant dynamics in Alpine Lakes fragile and rapidly changing ecosystems?
- Can potential environmental (also anthropogenic) perturbations on microbial communities be researched in the community composition, abundance and metabolic activities?

- Purpose of Data Collection:

The purpose of data collection in the MARMOT project is to:

- **Validate Robotic Systems:** Test and validate the functionality and reliability of the robotic and sensor technologies developed for long-term environmental monitoring in challenging alpine conditions.
- **Monitor Environmental Changes:** Gather continuous data on water quality, biological indicators, and ecological parameters in high Alpine Lakes to track changes induced by climate change and human activity.
- **Assess Ecological Status:** Collect water samples for chemical and biological analysis to better understand the ecological health of the lakes and assess their vulnerability to anthropogenic impacts.
- **Support Research and Innovation:** Provide data to enhance the development of advanced, modular robotic systems and sensors, contributing to the innovation and practical application of green technology in environmental monitoring.
- **Engage the Public:** Facilitate citizen science initiatives to involve local communities and schools in data collection, raising awareness and fostering public interest in environmental conservation.

Guidance: The MARMOT project involves a series of environmental monitoring studies using advanced robotic and sensor technologies. These studies aim to collect data on water quality, biological indicators, and ecological parameters in high mountain lakes in the European Alps. The primary purposes of data collection are to monitor environmental changes due to climate change and human activities, validate the performance of newly developed robotic systems, assess the ecological status of these sensitive environments, and support research and innovation in green technology. Additionally, the project engages local communities through citizen science initiatives, promoting public involvement and awareness in environmental conservation efforts.

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Related Policies: *Questions to consider:*

- Are there any existing procedures that you will base your approach on?
- Does your department/group have data management guidelines?
- Does your institution have a data protection or security policy that you will follow?
- Does your institution have a Research Data Management (RDM) policy?
- Does your funder have a Research Data Management policy?

[Are there any existing procedures that you will base your approach on?](#)

The procedures aligned with the EU's Horizon Europe framework, promoting Open Science and FAIR data management practices.

[Does your department/group have data management guidelines?](#)

No, but we adhere to Open Access policies and support data management aligned with the institutional framework for ethical research practices, as well as the Open Science and FAIR Data principles outlined in the funding and project guidelines. This includes ensuring research outputs are openly accessible and data are managed according to recognized standards for transparency, accessibility, and interoperability. Additionally, we utilize the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for storing, managing, and sharing research data, ensuring long-term preservation and compliance with FAIR principles.

[Does your institution have a data protection or security policy that you will follow?](#)

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A designated Data Protection Officer (DPO) ensures compliance with data protection laws, conducts Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs), and collaborates with national supervisory authorities

<https://www.cnr.it/en/dpo>

[Does your institution have a Research Data Management \(RDM\) policy?](#)

No, but the National Research Council (CNR) has a Research Data Management policy that is outlined in the Gaia Blu Data Management Plan (DMP). This plan provides a structured framework for managing research data in alignment with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring that all research data is properly curated and accessible for future use.

The Gaia Blu DMP outlines the following key aspects:

1. **FAIR Principles Compliance:** Ensures data is collected, managed, archived, and made freely available for scientific and public use, wherever possible.
2. **Data Preservation:** Defines standards for storing data during research activities and ensures long-term data preservation (minimum of 10 years).
3. **Embargo and Licensing:** Allows for embargo periods of up to three years post-research, after which data must be made available in trusted repositories with appropriate metadata and Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licenses (CC-BY 4.0).
4. **Data Harmonization:** Promotes standardized metadata and formats for interoperability and reuse.

<https://www.cnr.it/it/news/allegato/2962>

Does your funder have a Research Data Management policy?

Yes, Horizon Europe RDM policies include the obligation to make research outputs publicly accessible and to manage data in compliance with FAIR principles. Additionally, the PRIN project requires the publication of results in open access formats and repositories, ensuring following both national and European standards.

As part of the PRIN project's publication policies:

- Authorship is restricted to members of the research group, with exceptions only for conference proceedings organized by the beneficiary.
- Publications must include proper institutional and funding acknowledgments, such as the PNRR logos, CUP, and other identifiers as outlined in the Ministry's guidelines.
- Allowable costs include those related to open access publications, provided they align with project objectives and funding rules.

- Funder Policies: The project will follow the Research Data Management policy outlined by the European Union's Next Generation EU initiative.???

- Are there any formal standards that you will adopt?

Yes, the project will follow the Research Data Management (RDM) policies outlined by the European Union's NextGenerationEU initiative, aligning with the EU's broader goals for green, digital, and resilient recovery. This initiative encourages the implementation of the FAIR principles.

The MARMOT project, focuses on water resources analysis, climate action, and marine robotics, aligns with key EU strategic goals related to climate, health, food security, and the environment. These goals support the development of innovative technologies in marine robotics and water

monitoring, while also promoting green transport solutions and renewable energy sources. These areas are directly connected to the objectives of NextGenerationEU, which seeks to foster digital transformation, environmental sustainability, and cross-border collaboration in research. Additionally, following the FAIR principles for data treatment. Therefore, the MARMOT project complies with the EU's RDM policies and contributes to achieving these overarching societal challenges.

The following formal standards will be adopted:

1. **FAIR Principles:** The project will adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, ensuring that data is well-documented, accessible, and usable for future research. This aligns with the EU's NextGenerationEU initiative and Horizon Europe framework, which promote open science and data sharing across projects (European Commission, 2020).
2. **ISO 9001 (Quality Management Systems):** The project will follow ISO standards such as ISO 9001 to ensure data quality and proper documentation.
3. **Data Formats:** For data storage and dissemination, open formats such as CSV, NetCDF, or GeoJSON for geospatial data will be used to promote interoperability. (FAIR principles, Horizon Europe guidelines).
4. **Data Repositories:** Data will be deposited in trusted repositories such as Zenodo, PANGAEA, or similar, which comply with OpenAIRE and other European repositories' standards. These platforms support the long-term preservation of research data and ensure that data is findable and accessible.
5. **Licensing:** The data will be published with open licenses, such as Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY 4.0), ensuring that it can be freely reused, with appropriate attribution (CNR Gaia Blu DMP guidelines).

Guidance: List any other relevant funder, institutional, departmental or group policies on data management, data sharing and data security. Some of the information you give in the remainder of the DMP will be determined by the content of other policies. If so, point/link to them here.

1 Data summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

[UniTo] Chemical data obtained from previous sampling campaigns will be used to inform a targeted preparation of laboratory standards and, if possible, to temporally extend the chemical data series built in the frame of MARMOT for publication purposes.

[ISP] There is no previous microbiological data.

[IBE] AirQino will not make use of previous data

[INM] The ASV and UAV will not make use of previous data

[Unitus] We will leverage existing data from the literature to analyze the range of variables (pressure, temperature, chlorophyll-a fluorescence, turbidity, and dissolved oxygen) to be measured by our instrument and to extend the historical dataset for use in scientific publications.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

[UniTo] UNITO will collect water samples from multiple points across the glacial lakes. Samples will be identified using the following naming convention:

<Location>_<ISO_Date>_B<jj>_WS<kk>

where:

Location: IG (Indren Glacier) or EFG (Eastern Fellaria Glacier);

ISO_Date: date of sample collection in ISO 8601 format;

B<jj>: bottle identifier associated with a GNSS coordinate;

WS<kk>: water sample identifier, denoting the bottle's position in the sample set. The first digit represents the number of the WS (water sample) within a set of WSs, and the second digit represents the number of samples in that set.

Example: IG_20240730_B01_WS13 identifies the bottle 1 collected at Indren Glacier on July 30, 2024. The "WS13" indicates the first WS in a set of three WSs collected simultaneously.

Several sampling points will be selected across Indren Lake and Eastern Fellaria Lake. The water will be sampled using 50 mL plastic tubes, and each sampling point will be represented by a set of WSs. All samples will be stored at -20°C until analysis related to trace elements, organic pollutants will be conducted. The anions and cations in the lake water will be identified using ion chromatography techniques (DIONEX, Thermo Fisher, US). The dissolved organic carbon will be quantified with a TOC analyzer (Vario TOC Cube, Elementar, Germany). The sample aliquot used during analysis will no longer be available after the measurement. Chemical data exported from files generated by the instruments for chemical analyses will be stored as *.xls(x) and *.csv files. The collected data will also contribute to the calibration of the sensors.

[ISP] ISP will collect water samples from multiple points across the glacial lakes. Samples will be identified using the following naming convention described above by UniTo.

Sampling points will be selected in common with other research groups in the two lakes covered by the research (Indren Lake, Eastern Fellaria Lake). The water for microbiological analysis will be sampled using sterile test tubes and bottles, and each sampling point will be represented by a set of WSs. All samples will be stored cold (+4°C; -20°C) until analysis. Microbiological data generated will be stored as *.xls(x) *.csv and *.fastq files.

[IBE] AirQino will generate air quality data in the form of an ASCII string that will be stored into the project's NetCDF files.

[INM] The ASV will collect data from aquatic and air sensors, acoustic sensor, and robotic data in *.csv files. The UAV will collect images for land surrounding the lake in PNG format. The csv and PNG files will be used as input for the FOSS framework in order to obtain NetCDF self-describing files (*.nc).

[UniUd] data will be used to generate graphical user interfaces (GUIs) reporting the ASV telemetry and sensor information. Such GUIs will allow users to have at a glance an idea of both the behavior of the ASV and the current status of sensors.

[Unitus] Data will be generated in a readable format (ASCII string) and stored in CSV (Comma-Separated Values) files.[SB1]

[SB1]Chiedere a Juan se è possibile conservare i dati in netcdf nelle piattaforme di condivisione dei dati oceanografici (Emodnet e altri)

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

[UniTo] Chemical data generation and re-use of previous data will be used to investigate the chemical and ecological status of poorly studied Alpine glacial lakes and to assess possible anthropogenic impact. Selected datasets acquired through laboratory analyses will also serve for the calibration of sensors and for the evaluation of the effectiveness of automated sampling tools.

[ISP] Microbiological data acquisition will be used to assess both the water quality and the ecological status of poorly studied Alpine glacial lakes.

[IBE] AirQino will generate data that characterize the air quality above the Alpine glacial lakes in order to identify potential pollution events that might affect the glacial lakes' ecosystems thus contributing to increase the knowledge about a poorly investigated biome.

[INM] the data generated by INM will be used to monitor environmental parameters related to Alpine lake ecosystem status, to glacier runoff dynamics and their influence on Alpine glacial lake ecosystems. This data will contribute to the understanding processes affecting these ecosystems and help assess potential environmental changes over time. The data will also support the evaluation of automated monitoring systems used in the project, providing insights into the effectiveness of these technologies in collecting reliable environmental data.

[Unitus] The data collected by low-cost sensors integrated into the HELP platform will contribute to assessing water quality in Alpine glacial lakes, enabling the monitoring of environments that are particularly vulnerable to climate change and external disturbances.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

[UniTo] We expect max 50 MB of data.

[ISP] We expect max 20 GB of data.

[IBE] Each AirQino string is around 0.3 KB of data. Given an acquisition every 2 minutes, we expect AirQino to generate 9 KB of data per each hour of operation.

[INM] The Robotic platform will provide data each of the mission:

- Robot Telemetry: 50 to 250 MB each sampling mission; maximum 20 GB for the MARMOT project
- Sonar output 50-200 MB each sampling mission; maximum 20 GB for the MARMOT project

- Camera Data: 50 to 250 MB each sampling mission; maximum 20 GB for the MARMOT project
- Post-processing data for sonar is around 2 GB per mission, while camera data post-processing is approximately 5 GB; maximum 20 GB for MARMOT project.

[Unitus] We expect max 5 MB of data.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

[UniTo] Samples collected in the field during the MARMOT activities will be analyzed in laboratories using instruments for chemical analyses. Proper softwares, specifically connected to those instruments, will be used to extract and treat part of such data. In addition, re-used data originate from previous projects and research activities of the involved institutions.

[ISP] Microbiological samples collected in the field will be analyzed in laboratories using instruments for biological, biogeochemical and microbiological analyses. Proper softwares will be used to extract and treat microbiological data.

[IBE] Generated data come from the low-cost sensors onboard the AirQino.

[INM] The data collected by the ASV are generated by the full suite of sensors installed onboard, including: the AirQino platform for air quality monitoring, two high-cost and one low-cost multiparameter probes (High Altitude Low Cost Sensors) for the monitoring of water status, and a dual-frequency single-beam echosounder for lake-bed mapping. Additionally, the integration encompassed essential components for NGC (navigation, guidance, and control), such as a dual-frequency GNSS module with a multiband antenna that is also useful for precise georeferencing, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and a surface camera for remote control and Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) techniques.

The UAV collects images in PNG format for photogrammetry to create 3D models of the land surrounding the lake.

[Unitus] Data will be generated by low-cost sensors integrated within the HELP module to measure temperature, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, and chlorophyll-a fluorescence in the lakes.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

[UniTo] The generated chemical data will be useful for research institutions, environmental monitoring agencies, and stakeholders (focused on management of water resources in mountain areas).

[ISP] The pool of microbiological data will represent a baseline for these lakes and will be useful for research institutions, environmental monitoring agencies, and stakeholders.

[IBE] The generated air quality data will be useful for research institutions, environmental monitoring agencies and stakeholders focused on Alpine air quality and potential pollution events.

[INM] The generated data will be useful for the research community, in particular within the fields of Earth Sciences and Robotics Sciences. Adhering to FAIR principles ensures that the data collected can be exploited beyond the scientific realm, meaning policy makers, stakeholders, citizens and, in general, non-strictly scientific groups.

[Unitus] The generated data will be valuable for research centers studying the Alpine cryosphere, environmental monitoring agencies, and stakeholders focused on the management of water resources in mountain areas.

2 FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

[All] All datasets will be identified by Persistent Identifiers (PIDs). A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to each dataset. This PID will be issued automatically through a trusted repository such as Zenodo or PANGAEA, ensuring a stable reference for citation and retrieval even if the data's storage location changes.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?

[All] Yes, metadata will be created to ensure datasets are easily discoverable, understandable, and usable by both humans and machines

What metadata will be created?

1. **Descriptive Information:** (Dataset title, creators, description of the dataset, keywords and subject categories)
2. **Administrative Information:** (Date of data creation, licensing information, contact information)
3. **Technical Information:** (Data formats and software or tools required to process the data)
4. **Provenance Information:** (Data collection methods, quality control measures and Versioning history)

5. Structural Information: (Relationships between datasets and file organization within the dataset)

Metadata format, how does it appear?

The screenshot shows a web-based form titled "FAIR metadata" with a "Global Metadata" section. The form contains 20 input fields arranged in two columns. Each field has an information icon (i) to its left. The fields are: Title, Abstract, keywords, Conventions, PI name, PI email, PI institution, Platform, License, Dataset version, keywords vocabulary, Project long name, Data center (URL), Creator (URL), standard_name_vocabulary, id, processing_level, geospatial_vertical_max, geospatial_vertical_min, geospatial_vertical_positive, and geospatial_vertical_resolution, geospatial_vertical_units. Below the fields is a "Path to telemetry:" label with a file selection icon. At the bottom right, there are five buttons: "Default", "Clear", "Generate INI", "Generate NetCDF", and "Quit".

xarray.Dataset

```

- Dimensions:      (index: 65756)
- Coordinates:    (1)
- Data variables: (23)
  Attributes:
    title :          Raw Data Svalbard 2019
    summary :       Data collected during the Svalbard mission in 2019.
    keywords :     ctd,depth,svalbard
    conventions :  ACDD-1.3,CF-1.6
    creator_name :  Motta, Corrado
    creator_email : mail@cnr
    institution :   CNR-INM
    date_created :  2022-08-22T09:49:00+02:00
    platform :     satellite
    license :       None
    standard_name_... NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention Standard Name Table v79
    creator_url :   https://www.cnr.it/
    project :      INNOVAMARE
  
```

What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

Dublin Core

- **Purpose:** Dublin Core is a widely applicable standard for metadata that ensures essential information about datasets (such as title, creator, description, and date) is easily accessible. It is used for general metadata across various domains.
- **Application:** Utilize Dublin Core for basic descriptive metadata, ensuring that your datasets are discoverable, identifiable, and properly attributed.

DataCite Metadata Schema

- **Purpose:** Specifically designed for datasets in academic and research contexts, DataCite offers detailed metadata elements like data type, funding sources, and research project identifiers. It's widely used for datasets in scholarly publications.
- **Application:** Use DataCite when describing datasets to be shared in academic research, ensuring the dataset is well-documented with necessary details, such as funding sources, project identifiers, and more.

ISO 19115 (For Geospatial and Environmental Datasets)

- **Purpose:** ISO 19115 provides a standard for documenting geospatial data, ensuring that spatial and environmental datasets are well-described and can be shared and used across different platforms and disciplines.
- **Application:** This standard will be used to describe metadata related to environmental and geospatial data, such as UAV imagery, air and water quality measurements, and lake-bed mapping.

EML (Ecological Metadata Language) (For Ecological and Environmental Research)

- **Purpose:** EML is a standard for documenting ecological and environmental research datasets. It provides standardized metadata for environmental data collection methods, quality control, and more.
- **Application:** EML will be used to describe environmental monitoring data, such as data from water samples, air quality sensors, and other ecological research datasets.

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions (For Climate and Forecast Data in NetCDF Format)

- **Purpose:** CF Conventions ensure that climate and forecast data, typically in NetCDF format, are described in a way that makes the data interoperable and easy to understand by researchers and systems. It covers key dimensions such as time, latitude, and longitude.
- **Application:** This standard will be used for climate data stored in NetCDF format, ensuring the data is described with the appropriate physical and temporal dimensions.

ISO 8601 (For Date and Time)

- **Purpose:** ISO 8601 standardizes the representation of dates and times to avoid confusion. It ensures uniformity and consistency when handling temporal data.
- **Application:** Use ISO 8601 to format all date and time data in your metadata, ensuring consistency and clarity across all datasets (e.g., 2024-12-03T14:30:00).

[In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.](#)

While established metadata standards exist, there is currently no standardized vocabulary for terms used in robotic variables. Therefore, we will adopt existing metadata standards to ensure that data is well-documented, accessible, and reusable. The metadata will include essential information such as dataset titles, descriptions, keywords, creators, temporal and spatial coverage, data formats, and licensing details. Additional details, such as data collection methods, quality control measures, and technical specifications—including software tools used and versioning history—will also be provided.

To address the absence of a shared vocabulary for robotic variables, we will rely on internal resources, such as the periodically updated metadata lists maintained in spreadsheets and the pipeline available on GitHub. This approach will support the definition and confirmation of variable names and metadata, ensuring consistency and interoperability.

A standard template will be used to create metadata for each dataset, which will be stored in trusted repositories. This approach will adhere to Open Science and FAIR Data principles, promoting transparency, accessibility, and long-term usability of the data.

[Outline the most important metadata elements \(recommended ISO 19115 geographic metadata standard\)](#)

[INM] The NetCDF files (*.nc), created using the *.csv files in input to the FOSS framework, will be self-describing files, containing global metadata according to the ISO 19115 standard and variable metadata following the Climate and Forecast convention as standard vocabulary.

Which naming conventions for your data files will you follow?

The approach suggested by ELIXIR (2021) Research Data Management Kit. A deliverable from the EU-funded ELIXIR-CONVERGE project (grant agreement 871075). URL:

<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org> is the one here reported the structure of the collected Data:

STRUCTURE	EXPLANATION	EXAMPLE
project/	<i>Project Identifier</i>	MARMOT/
README.txt	<i>file and folder description</i>	
- code/		
- data/	<i>raw and primary data (never edit!)</i>	data/
-- Data Integration Files/	<i>Spreadsheets describing variable headers, sensors outputs and data conversion algorithms</i>	-- Data Integration Files/
-- location_identifier/	<i>where data were collected</i>	Indren Glacier
--- date/	<i>date and time in ISO 8601 format (yyyymmdd)</i>	20241125/
---- raw/	<i>raw data downloaded from the vehicle untouched</i>	raw/
---- corollary/	<i>logs files containing the description of the system state and data recording process</i>	corollary/
---- pictures/		
---- utilia/	<i>contains useful information about the mission, e.g. list of material, people participating, tips for the preparation of the field mission</i>	utilia/
----- mission_number/	<i>mission numbers (indicating separate data collection missions)</i>	M001/ M002/
logbook data.csv, data.log,	<i>codified es below reported</i>	MARMOT_2024 1125T1500Z_T_ USV.csv
---- results/	<i>output from workflows and analyses</i>	results/
----- logs/	<i>logs from the different analysis steps</i>	logs/
----- figures/		figures/
----- reports/		reports/
----- tables/		tables/
----- doc/	<i>documentation of the study</i>	doc/
----- code/	<i>code needed to go from input files to final results</i>	code/

Example:

MARMOT/data/Indren Glacier/20241125/raw/M001/240902-124854_marmot.log

project/data/location_identifier/date/raw/mission_number/data.log

Bottle sampling:

FILE NAME STRUCTURE	EXPLANATION	EXAMPLE
PROJECT_	Project Identifier	MARMOT_
DATE_	Date and time in ISO 8601 format (e.g., 2024-11-25 at 15:00 UTC).	20241125T1500Z_
TYPE_	<p>Data Type Identifiers:</p> <p>Telemetry USV: T_USV</p> <p>Telemetry UAV: T_UAV</p> <p>Bottle+Watersampe: Bjj_AWSkk (Bottle identifiers_Water sample identifiers, denoting the bottle's position in the sample set collected automatically)</p> <p>Bottle+Watersampe: Bjj_HWSkk (Bottle identifiers_Water sample identifiers, denoting the bottle's position in the sample set collected by hand)</p>	<p>B01, B02, B03, etc.: Bottle identifiers.</p> <p>WS13, WS23, WS33, etc.: Water sample identifiers, denoting the bottle's position in the sample</p>
v_	vxx: Version of the dataset	v1

An example is reported below

/MARMOT

 /Indren Glacier

 /2024-11-25

 /M001

 MARMOT_20241125T1500Z_T_USV.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1501Z_T_UAV.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1501Z_B01_AWS13_v1.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1505Z_B02_AWS23_v1.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1515Z_B03_AWS33_v1.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1520Z_B04_AWS13_v1.csv

 /M002

 MARMOT_20241125T1600Z_T_USV.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1601Z_T_UAV.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1605Z_B01_AWS13_v1.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1615Z_B02_AWS23_v1.csv

 MARMOT_20241125T1620Z_B03_AWS33_v1.csv

2.2. Making data accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions or embargo), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions. Do this for each type of dataset you will create.

The datasets will be shared through well-established and trusted data repositories such as Zenodo or Pangaea. As well as local.

Chemical data obtained by water samples collected by hand will be uploaded to Zenodo. This repository ensures long-term preservation of data deposits and is projected to be maintained for the operational lifetime of its host institution, CERN, which is defined as at least the next twenty years.

Do you plan to make the data and metadata available on trusted data repository, for instance an institutional, a thematic or a geographic repository?

Yes, Zenodo, Pangaea or Institutional Repositories.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The project will open-standard file formats for data sharing, ensuring broad accessibility:

- **CSV (Comma-Separated Values):** Suitable for tabular data, such as measurements of temperature, depth, and other parameters.
- **GeoJSON:** For geospatial data, including points, lines, and polygons with associated attributes.
- **NetCDF:** For multi-dimensional environmental data, such as temperature profiles over time and depth.
- **TIFF/GeoTIFF:** For photogrammetry outputs, such as raster-based maps and images.

These formats can be accessed using standard software tools available on most operating systems.

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

To open and view the data (e.g., importing CSV files into Excel, HTML or Python).

To visualize geospatial data using GIS software (e.g., loading GeoJSON in QGIS).

Metadata Standards documentation of metadata standards used (e.g., ISO 19115 for geospatial data, Dublin Core for descriptive metadata).

[Is it possible to include the relevant software \(e.g. in open source code\)?](#)

Developed scripts or software to process or analyze the data, these will be included alongside the dataset through popular platforms like GitHub or GitLab that can host the code with proper documentation.

[Where will the documentation and code be deposited?](#)

Zenodo, as mentioned before, and internal repository of MARMOT project.

2.3. Making data interoperable

[Assess how you will capture and store the elements that facilitate or ensure the interoperability of your data \(giving preference to open and standard data formats\).](#)

Guidance: in the following table a non-exhaustive list of general file formats is shown

Category	Data type	Recommended	Non-recommended
General data formats	Text	TXT, HTML, RTF, PDF/A	DOC, PPT
	Tabular	CSV, TSV, SPSS portable (.por)	XLS
	Images	TIFF, JPEG2000, PNG	GIF, JPG
	Multimedia	Container: AVI, WAV, MP4, Ogg Codec: Theora, Dirac, FLAC	Windows Media Video, QuickTime, H264
	Structured	XML, RDF	RDBMS

[Specify whether you will be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set.](#)

Guidance: the ISO 19115 geographic metadata standard is recommended together with the use of standard vocabularies (e.g. Climate and Forecast CF convention) to provide data access covering many different fields.

[INM] The syntactic interoperability will be ensured by the use of open and standard data format:

*.csv, *.nc for ASV data;

*.txt for echologger data

The semantic interoperability will be ensured by the use of standard naming convention:

- Climate and Forecast for environmental variables;
- Naming convention (not an official standard but a “standard de facto”) for marine robotics variables from Fossen, T. I. (1999). Guidance and control of ocean vehicles. *University of Trondheim, Norway, Printed by John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, England, ISBN: 0 471 94113 1, Doctors Thesis.*

2.4. Increase data re-use

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

[All] Once the embargo period has passed, the data will be released under CC-BY 4.0 license

Guidance: open science policies want to stimulate openly accessible data, with maximal reusability. In order to facilitate this, open, up-front and machine readable licenses are preferred, such as those on <https://creativecommons.org/licenses>.

Specify when the data will be made available for reuse. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.

Data Availability:

Data generated during the project will be made openly available immediately upon publication of the project's results, ensuring accessibility for reuse by other researchers, stakeholders, and the general public.

Embargo Policy:

In certain cases, an embargo period may be imposed to protect pre-publication findings or to comply with confidentiality agreements related to ongoing collaborations. The embargo period will not exceed 2 years from the date of data collection unless explicitly justified and approved by

relevant authorities or funding agencies and in accordance with the MARMOT project coordinator.

Justifications for Embargo:

- Exceptional research findings related to environmental discoveries that may require additional validation or policy considerations before public release.
- Protection of intellectual property during patent application processes.
- Securing competitive advantage for ongoing research or commercial development.
- Compliance with ethical considerations, including participant privacy and data sensitivity.
- Collaboration agreements with third parties requiring temporary restricted access.

Data Release After Embargo:

Following the expiration of the embargo period, all datasets will be released in publicly accessible repositories with proper metadata and documentation to facilitate reuse.

[Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why](#)

Data and metadata will be made fully reusable by third parties after the project ends. Open and standard formats (CSV, JSON) and detailed metadata ensure compatibility with various tools and platforms.

[Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable](#)

Data will be maintained and accessible for at least 10 years after the project ends, aligning with FAIR data management principles.

[Describe how you will capture data harmonization, quality assurance and data curation processes](#)

Harmonization Processes: Use of controlled vocabularies (e.g., CF Standard Names) and standardized units (e.g., SI units) to ensure data consistency. Integration of metadata standards like Dublin Core and ISO 19115. To mention, robotics has no standard vocab..

Quality Assurance Measures: Automated scripts to verify data format and integrity. Check up of datasets prior to release. Include error logs and confidence intervals with data.

Data Curation: Periodic updates to metadata to reflect any changes in repository structure or data formats.

3 Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

You should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for reuse, in line with the FAIR principles.

Water Samples:

With MARMOT project water samples collected in automatic for a variety of purposes are foreseen to conduct different analyses, including investigations related to trace elements, organic pollutants, chlorophyll levels, and microbiology.

When working with robotic platforms that collect both digital data and water samples, it's essential to track the water samples alongside the robot's telemetry. This ensures that the sample was collected precisely when the onboard sensors were capturing relevant data, and the robot was in the specific position.

To achieve this, robust tracking systems are necessary. These systems provide instantly accessible data associated with devices, samples, and experimental results for all collaborators involved. Given that the water sampler comprises various automated water samples, we need to assign a unique name, possibly associated with a QR code, to each water sample acquired. The Research Data Alliance (RDA) gives suggestions and references to practical resources and tools that can be useful to manage and share data on physical samples. Among these, two tools that could be useful for managing the samples collected in the MARMOT project are the use of the International Geo Sample Number (IGSN) persistent identifier and the System for Earth Sample Registration (SESAR) repository where to record the metadata relating to the physical samples.

Analogous to a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), the IGSN can be used as a label for samples that allows for unambiguous naming and persistent access to information about the sample. Moreover, the registration of the sample on the SESAR portal provides label printing services that contain the sample name, IGSN, QR code linking to the sample metadata profile page and customizable additional metadata fields.

To implement this effectively, it's crucial to associate a unique sample name acting as reference code for each water sample.

Water Sample Coding System collected automatically:

When associating codes with each water sample, we can use the following format:

<Project>_<Location>_<ISO_Date and Time>_M<iii>_B<jj>_WS<kk>

FORMAT COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION	EXAMPLES
<Project>	Project identifier (e.g., MARMOT or MRM).	MARMOT
<Location>	Sampling locality name (e.g., Indren).	INDREN
<ISO_Date and Time>	ISO date and time of first sample (e.g., 20240604T1531Z).	20240604T1531Z
M<iii>	Mission identifier, three-digit number distinguishing restarts (e.g., M002).	M002
B<jj>	Bottle identifier, two-digit number uniquely identifying bottles (e.g., B03).	B01
AWS<kk>	Automatic Water Sample identifier, first digit = WS set number, second = samples per set (e.g., AWS15).	AWS13
HWS<kk>	Hand-collected Water Sample identifier, first digit = HWS set number, second = samples per set (e.g., HWS11).	HWS11

As a general example, let's consider a water sampler with 8 bottles. Suppose we want to identify a water sample collected in Indren on June 4, 2024, during the second mission, which includes 3 water samples, 2 water samples, and 3 water samples. The resulting codes would be as follows:

MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:31Z_M002_B01_AWS13
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:31Z_M002_B02_AWS23
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:31Z_M002_B03_AWS33
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:42Z_M002_B04_AWS12
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:42Z_M002_B05_AWS22
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:53Z_M002_B06_AWS13
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:53Z_M002_B07_AWS23
MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T15:53Z_M002_B08_AWS33

Sampling methods for physical samples collected by hand:

Hand Water samples are collected near the outlet and along the shoreline around the lake, in both study areas. At least four water samples are collected at each sampling point using 50 mL plastic tubes. The samples intended for microbial analysis are immediately sealed with lab film, and, like those for chemical analysis, are stored at -20°C.

In the field, the label attached to the sample would be :

“M002_B01_HWS13”,

and in the lab and later in the SESAR portal, the associated label will be:

“MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T1542Z_M002_B04_HWS13”

It is important to ensure that the QR code and alphanumeric code are linked in the sample management system for effective traceability and accessibility.

Planned Approach for Telemetry Data Integration with Water Samples

We plan to establish a procedure for integrating telemetry data with water sample records to enhance traceability and accessibility. As part of this process, we will create a telemetry file named using a consistent format, similar to the SESAR naming convention. For example: MARMOT_INDREN_20240604T1542Z_M002_B04_AWS12.csv.

This telemetry file will contain actual or median parameters collected by the robotic platform during a defined time interval (e.g., the last 1 minute). The data may include sensor readings, environmental variables, and other relevant information captured by the robot.

To ensure a strong link between the telemetry data and the water sample, the telemetry file will be attached directly to the water sample record. This approach allows anyone accessing the water sample information to also retrieve the corresponding telemetry data, providing context and supporting further analysis.

Additionally, we aim to increase accessibility by integrating the telemetry data as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) within the metadata of the SESAR record. This will enable researchers and collaborators to access the full telemetry dataset associated with each water sample through standardized and persistent identifiers.

By implementing this approach, we will create a comprehensive and well-documented link between water samples, telemetry data, and research datasets, ensuring data reliability, traceability, and long-term usability.

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

[UniTo] No costs are expected for chemical data.

[ISP] No costs are expected for microbiological data.

[IBE] No costs are expected for the AirQino data

[INM] no additional costs are expected for making the data FAIR. Data will be stored in NetCDF format, and the necessary storage and archiving will be handled through institutional systems. In case other expenses are needed they will be covered by funding from INM internal resources.

[Unitus] No additional costs are expected for the data acquired by the low-cost sensors integrated into the HELP platform.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

[UniTo] Prof. Maria Martin (Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, University of Torino) will be responsible for chemical data management in MARMOT.

[ISP] Alessandro Cosenza (Institute of Polar Sciences of Messina) will be responsible for microbiological data management in MARMOT.

[IBE] Federico Carotenuto (Institute for BioEconomy, National Research Council of Italy) will be responsible for AirQino data management in MARMOT

[INM] Ali Alakbar Karaki and Angelo Odetti (Institute of Marine Engineering, National Research Council) will be responsible for ASV data management

[Unitus] Simone Bonamano (Laboratory of Experiment Oceanology and Marine Ecology of the Department of Ecological and Biological Science, University of Tuscia)

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

[UniTo] During the project activities, chemical data will be stored on IT systems belonging to the involved researchers. Chemical data from MARMOT will be retained for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

[ISP] During the project activities, microbiological data will be stored on IT systems belonging to the involved researchers. Chemical data from MARMOT will be retained for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

[IBE] AirQino data will be stored in MARMOT project's NetCDF files ...

[INM] data will be stored in NetCDF format on institutional IT systems managed by involved researchers. Significant datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories, such as Zenodo, to ensure long-term preservation and accessibility.

[Unitus] Data acquired by marine low-cost sensors integrated into the HELP platform will be stored on IT systems managed by the involved researchers. These data will be retained for a minimum of 5 years following the conclusion of the MARMOT project.

5 Data Security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

[UniTo] Chemical data will be under the protection of IT data storage main technologies from the University of Torino.

[ISP] Microbiological data will be under the protection of IT data storage main technologies from the Institute of Polar Sciences of Messina.

[INM] The ASV data, once collected onboard the vehicle during field testing, will be transferred to a local server in the CNR-INM laboratory and stored in various personal SSD.

[Unitus] Data acquired by marine low-cost sensors integrated into the HELP platform will be protected by the main IT data storage technologies at the University of Tuscia.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

[UniTo] In case of chemical data of environmental relevance, potentially usable for publication, data will be uploaded to Zenodo, which supports long-term preservation of data deposits, as the repository is projected to be maintained for the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, defined as at least the next twenty years.

[ISP] The microbiological chemical data will be uploaded to Zenodo or Italian Arctic Data Center, which supports long-term preservation of data deposits. Nucleotide sequences have been deposited in the NCBI GenBank database.

[UniUd] Communications between the ASV and other devices (e.g., smartphones, laptops, cloud servers) will be authenticated, according to high security standards.

[INM] Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation. For example, Zenodo, a repository maintained by CERN, will be used.

[Unitus] The data will be securely stored in Zenodo, which supports the long-term preservation of data deposits and is maintained by CERN.

6 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

[UniTo] We are not aware of any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing.

[ISP] To date, we are not aware of any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing.

[IBE] IBE will make clear that air-quality generated with AirQino have no legal impact (since only air quality data from official environmental protection agencies have legal validity). Beside that, IBE is not aware of any ethics or legal issue that can have an impact on data sharing.

[INM] We are not aware of any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing.

[Unitus] We are not aware of any ethical or legal issues that could impact data sharing.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

[UniTo] No personal data will be collected by UniTo.

[ISP] No personal data will be collected by UniTo.

[IBE] No personal data will be collected by AirQino

[INM] No personal data will be collected by the ASV systems

[UniUd] No personal data will be used in the generation of the user interfaces.

[Unitus] No personal data will be collected by Unitus

7 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones- (please list and briefly describe them)?

[UniTo] The University of Turin is not planning to use other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.

[ISP] ISP is not planning to use other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.

[IBE] IBE is not planning to use other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.

[INM] The project primarily adheres to the Horizon Europe and PRIN guidelines, including the FAIR principles for data management. No additional procedures are planned beyond these established frameworks.

[Unitus] The University of Tuscia does not plan to use any other national, funding agency, sector-specific, or departmental procedures for data management.

5 References

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DCC. (2013). *Checklist for a Data Management Plan*. v.4.0. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans>

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https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_organisation.html#what-is-the-best-way-to-name-a-file

“FAIRmat, Guide to Writing a Research Data Management Plan”, version 1.0, 25 March, 2023;

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